

Teaching children about

the nature of science by exploring big questions

Laura Hackett and Sherralyn Simpson recount how they have developed children's understanding of how science and other disciplines relate

Figure 1 Working together to explore big questions

LASAR (Learning about Science and Religion) has been exploring different opportunities to engage children with practical science enquiry to develop children's understanding of the nature of science and how they suppose science connects to 'big questions'. We have interacted through a range of epistemic insight investigations within the traditional classroom setting alongside innovative extracurricular sessions.

After-school club opportunities

Laura Hackett

At the beginning of our first session, I ask primary school children the question: 'What is science?' The answers I usually get are: 'experiments', 'explosions', 'facts' or 'proof'. The findings support previous studies, which found that children's ideas about science are missing some key ideas and that this is due in large part to how children interpret their experiences in science lessons at school (Billingsley and Hardman, 2017; Billingsley, Abedin and Nassaji, 2019). So-called 'recipe' investigations follow a step-by-step set of instructions to reach a predetermined outcome and leave many children supposing that investigating scientifically provides an easy or certain solution to a problem. The power and limitations of science are not given sufficient attention in school science lessons.

Figure 2
Children need to learn about the power and limitations of science so they can evaluate sensationalist headlines

Some children may also encounter sensationalised headlines about science in the media such as: 'Woolly mammoths will be brought back to life in SIX years, scientists claim' (*The Sun*, 27.9.21), 'Scientists solve the mystery of why women are always colder than men' (*The Sun*, 2.11.21) and 'Simple blood test could tell if you're going to be struck down with dementia in the next five years, experts say' (*Mail Online*, 11.10.21) (Figure 2). It adds to a false impression in children's minds that science has or soon will have the answer to all our questions.

Gaps in science education

These misperceptions about the power and limitations of science sit alongside confusion and gaps in children's reasoning about the ways in which science and other disciplines can work together to create new knowledge. Epistemic insight (or 'knowledge about knowledge') is the term we use to describe children's scholarly expertise and understanding about how knowledge is formed, the power and limitations of science, and how science and other subject disciplines can interact and work together. It is important to strengthen children's epistemic insight while they are in primary schools, before they move on to secondary school where disciplines like science, English and history are broken up into neat chunks, and lessons delivered in isolation from one another

– a practice we call 'entrenched subject compartmentalisation'. This impacts on children's curiosity about, and capacity to explore, the 'big questions' that bridge science, religion and the wider humanities, such as those about human personhood and the nature of reality. Examples are 'What does it mean to be alive?' and 'Will humans ever live and work on other planets?'

Our research has found that many children are interested in asking these big questions and want to think about how science can work together with other disciplines to explore these topics. However, a typical school timetable focuses on learning about one discipline at a time. For example, in science lessons children are generally given a question predetermined by the teacher and are moved quickly on to reaching the correct answer by the end of the lesson. It means that they are unlikely to be encouraged to think about history in a science lesson, or science in a religious education lesson, and they often lack an understanding of the distinctiveness of each discipline, and how disciplines might work together to think about shared topics or questions. In so doing, children miss out on the process of thinking more deeply about the preferred questions, methods and norms of thought of that discipline and how working with a given disciplinary lens shapes and limits the answer that you get.

In order to develop children's understanding of the nature of science, one important strategy is to encourage them to think about how science fits within into the wider range of ways of knowing they meet in school, such as asking what types of questions are good ones for science, whether all questions are good for science and how other disciplines such as history or religious education might help us to address a given question, if at all. An example of this is the question 'Can a robot be like a human?' Through the lens of science we can explore this question by making links to the characteristics of life: does the robot move or sense its environment? Through scientific

observation we may conclude that the robot's physical appearance also seems to be very much like a human. But we may also feel there is something very *unhuman* about a robot, and examining questions asked in a different discipline can provide further insight. Religious education or philosophy can bring in the idea of a soul and/or what we believe about why humans take the actions they do, the emotions people feel about their actions and the need for relationships. The arts highlight what it means to be human in terms of having an appreciation of beauty, music and creativity, and so on.

Teaching in practice

This brings us back to my discussion of our after-school 'science and big questions' club at a local primary school, with children from years 4 to 6 (ages 8–11). Each week we explore a big question, such as 'Why do we need water?' or 'What does it mean to be alive?' The children take part in a science investigation, such as building a motorised 'bristlebot' (Figure 3) or using diffraction glasses to explore the rainbow of colours found in visible light (Figure 4), before moving on to explore the topic from the perspective of other disciplines.

Beginning the sessions with a science investigation is a great way to get children 'hooked' and excited about conducting practical, hands-on science (when they use our resources, the children each get their own set of equipment for each activity). It also gets children thinking about the nature of science, what makes a question a good one for science to answer, and what makes science distinctive as a discipline.

One of the main things we emphasise in our resources is the importance of

Figure 3 Beginning with a science investigation such as building a motorised 'bristlebot' is a great way to get children 'hooked'

Figure 4 Using diffraction glasses to explore the colours found in visible light

scientific observation and ensuring children become familiar with hearing and using the terminology of 'observe' and 'make observations' so that they are developing their understanding of science as primarily concerned with making observations of the natural world.

In our experience, teachers may tend to shy away from using this scientific language, whereas the children participating in the activities we run pick it up very quickly when it is consistently reinforced by members of the research team. Indeed, after just one epistemic insight workshop, children in our weekly club have been overheard using phrases such as '*I observed...*' when an hour previously they had reported no known association between science and observation. After their second after-school club session, 93% of the children used the term '*observe*' when writing up the findings of their investigation.

The other main focus of our sessions is providing exposure to big questions about human personhood and the nature of reality. While children demonstrate (from survey and interview responses) an interest and desire to think and talk about these questions, we are also made aware of the lack of opportunity for many of them to do so, both at school and in the home. What has been interesting while running these after-school workshops, is the propensity for children to think about these as 'big questions for science' rather than big questions that science can help inform our thinking about in conjunction with other disciplines.

For instance, when asked at the start of a session on colour, '*Tell me everything you know about rainbows*', all the children gave answers relating to science, referencing sunlight and raindrops. Not one child in the group being questioned could think outside the scientific paradigm by suggesting that rainbows were symbolic (such as the religious story of Noah's Ark) or held cultural importance (such as the rainbow pictures displayed in windows during the COVID-19 lockdown), despite pictures of rainbows in these contexts being projected onto the whiteboard.

It is clear, when encouraging children to think of the questions, methods, and norms of thoughts of other disciplines, that this is a complex and novel task. Children do not have enough information about the types of knowledge with which each discipline is concerned to be able to confidently identify a question that is good for science and a question that another discipline may ask. We do not presume to be able to impart this understanding after a handful of workshops, but we are heartened to see that children as young as 8 years old can begin to think in a multidisciplinary way with guidance and support.

Figure 5 shows some multidisciplinary posters by children in years 4, 5 and 6, in which the theme of '*Why do we have rainbow colours?*' was explored from different perspectives. At the beginning of the session the children were unable to move past the scientific question of '*How are rainbows formed?*' By the end, children were able to generate alternative questions for other disciplines, such as: '*What do colours mean?*', '*What would happen if we didn't have colours?*', '*How do colours keep us safe?*', '*Where in the world gets the most rainbows?*', '*Why are bubbles so pretty?*' and '*Who decided that red means hot and blue means cold?*'

The breadth of questions arising from primary-aged children's minds is fascinating, and demonstrates not only an interest in asking and exploring a range of disciplines, but also that young children have the capacity to grow and develop this area of knowledge.

Figure 5 Children's posters exploring rainbow colours from different perspectives

Classroom opportunities: *'You are what you eat – or are you?'*

Sherralyn Simpson

This workshop starts by asking children to discuss the statement '*You are what you eat!*' in small groups. Each group mind-maps their ideas, and then they present their shared reflections on the extent to which they agree or disagree with the statement. The next step is for children to address the big question, '*Are you what you eat?*' To help with this, the question is put in the centre of an epistemological tool known as the Discipline Wheel (Figure 6), which encourages children to identify and discuss how different disciplines can help address the question. This tool also facilitates educators in explaining that different disciplines have preferred questions, methods and norms of thought.

Through the workshop children gain new insights into the relationships between science and other ways of knowing, developing what it means to be good with knowledge and helping to address misperceptions about the nature of knowledge drawn from everyday life or as an unintended consequence of their educational experiences. For example, children will consider how science can help us to address the question, with a number of approaches considered, such as nutritional surveys and investigations into the digestive process.

Educators can highlight the nature of science by asking an additional

Figure 6 The Discipline Wheel helps children to explore how a question can be addressed by different disciplines

smaller question to the big question displayed in the Discipline Wheel. For instance, the question ‘*What happens to food when it enters the body?*’ would investigate the main functions and parts of the digestive system in humans. How? Those leading the session could elicit and expand children’s ideas about the digestive process through a fun visual such as a digestive system apron (Figure 7), followed with drawing and labelling their own paper version of the digestive system to identify what happens to food when it enters the body. Through practical science enquiry, children observe this process by mixing breakfast biscuits with orange-coloured water (to represent stomach acid) and clear water (saliva) in a plastic bag simulating the stomach. The contents are broken down and mashed up in the

Figure 7 A fun visual can help elicit children’s ideas

‘stomach’ before being added to one leg of a pair of tights (small intestine). Children enjoy squeezing the liquid out, which represents the nutrients our bodies need, and observe that what remains is solid waste in the large intestine, This is subsequently squeezed out of the tights, removing it from the body! A far less messy alternative is to observe the digestive process by squeezing scrunched-up newspaper (food) through tights (digestive system).

We are discovering that the big question ‘*Are you what you eat?*’ is an engaging and exciting way to encourage children to explore the power and limitations of science, while helping to address and identify misconceptions about the nature of knowledge. The aim here is for children to notice that we can frame a smaller question that is more amenable to science and respond through observations of the natural world, providing opportunity to recognise the nature of science. Scientifically investigating the smaller question, ‘*What happens to food when it enters the body?*’, informs thinking about a bigger complex aspect of our lives – our relationship with food. Learning science that incorporates both substantive and disciplinary knowledge enhances children’s perception of being ‘good’ at science, viewed as ‘crucial’ to them developing interest and confidence in science (Ofsted, 2021a).

Workshop facilitators can then explain that conceptions of health and healthy lifestyles are influenced by a multitude of factors that go beyond science. By incorporating the Discipline Wheel, differing perspectives provide insight into these. For example, through the humanities they learn about the impact of societal influences or geographical location upon dietary approaches such as veganism or a Mediterranean diet, while religious approaches to diet, such as dietary laws (e.g. kosher or halal), provide engagement with the notion that science and religion are not necessarily incompatible. Combining disciplinary perspectives generates opportunity to be ‘good with knowledge’ in a scientific age by exploring big ideas, such as the pursuit

of a good life within religious education (Ofsted, 2021b), developing a wise and compassionate learner.

At end of the session the workshop facilitator then explains the complex nature of big questions in relation to human personhood and the nature of reality by providing other examples, such as ‘*Why does the Earth exist?*’ or ‘*Can robots think for themselves?*’ Such illustrations provide opportunity to explore what science, religion and the wider humanities have to say about a big question, through the distinct approaches and norms of thought of a range of disciplines. Consequently, the vision and findings from the workshop indicate that epidemic insight pedagogy increases children’s understanding of how science and other disciplines relate, encouraging them to be curious and open-minded about how to interpret and approach big questions. Children are then better placed to think critically about the nature, application and communication of knowledge in their learning.

References

Billingsley, B. and Hardman, M. (2017) Epistemic insight: teaching and learning about the nature of science in real-world and multidisciplinary arenas. *School Science Review*, **98**(365), 57–58.

Billingsley, B., Abedin, M. and Nassaji, M. (2019) Primary school students’ perspectives on questions that bridge science and religion: findings from a survey study in England. *British Educational Research Journal*, **46**(1), 177–204.

Ofsted (2021a) *Research review series: science*. London: Ofsted. Available at: www.gov.uk/government/publications/research-review-series-science/research-review-series-science

Ofsted (2021b) *Research review series: religious education*. London: Ofsted. Available at: www.gov.uk/government/publications/research-review-series-religious-education/research-review-series-religious-education

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